

PRINCIPLES OF LANDSCAPE DESIGN AND LAND USE AT THE LEVEL OF A TERRITORIAL COMMUNITY

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Abstract

The article examines a number of important positions in order to study the principles of landscape design and land use at the level of the territorial community, which involves analyzing the main trends in planning the development of the land use system, in particular: property relations, functional orientation, social significance, and land capitalization.

Keywords: landscape design, land use, land management, territorial community, anthropogenic impact, land plot, landscape, map.

Land use is a way of utilizing land resources for various purposes, such as agriculture, forestry, industry, construction, recreation, etc. Land use determines how land is used, what activities are carried out on it, and what impacts they have on the environment. Changes in land use can have significant consequences for landscapes, affecting their structure and functioning [7].

Let us identify the factors that influence landscape transformation.

I. Natural factors include all natural processes that affect landscapes. These can be climatic conditions, geological processes, hydrological regimes, biological processes and other natural phenomena [6]:

1) Climatic factors such as temperature, precipitation, wind, and solar radiation have a significant impact on landscape formation and change. For example, rising temperatures due to global warming can lead to changes in vegetation and soils.

2) Geological processes, such as volcanic activity, tectonic movements, erosion, and deposition, can change the topography and structure of landscapes. For example, earthquakes can cause changes in topography and create new geomorphic forms.

3) Water processes, such as river flows, lakes, waterfalls, glaciers, and groundwater, influence landscape formation and change. Changes in hydrologic regimes can cause erosion, siltation, changes in river channels, and other transformations.

II. Anthropogenic factors include all human activities that affect landscapes. These can include agriculture, urbanization, industry, infrastructure construction, and other forms of land use:

1) Intensive agriculture and livestock farming can lead to changes in soil, land degradation, destruction of natural vegetation, and pollution of water resources. For example, excessive use of pesticides and fertilizers can negatively affect soil and water quality.

2) Urban sprawl and infrastructure construction change natural landscapes into urbanized areas. This can lead to the destruction of natural ecosystems, changes in hydrological regimes, increased surface water runoff, and environmental pollution.

3) Industrial activities such as mining, manufacturing and construction can have a significant impact on landscapes. It can lead to air, water, and soil pollution, as well as changes in the relief and structure of land [5].

Landscape design and land use of territorial communities are based on systemic, genetic, historical and geographical, regional, typological, landscape and ecological scientific approaches that allow to assess the peculiarities of genesis, patterns of development, functioning of landscape units involved in agricultural development, and to establish trends in their development in changing resource and environmental conditions. Given that the basis for developing the geographical framework for managing landscapes used for food security is a landscape map, it is important to select the most informative principles of landscape design and land use.

Spatial planning, which should become a key function of public administration, is designed to create a rational territorial organization of land use and take into account the interrelationships between different lands, while ensuring environmental protection and a balance between social, economic, and environmental interests. When planning, it is important to take into account the impact of all sectors of the country's economy on existing land uses, which makes spatial planning an essential tool for promoting sustainable development of territories and improving the quality of life of the population.

Table 1 summarizes the basic principles of landscape design and land use to ensure food security in the region.

Principles of landscape design and land use at the level of the territorial community	
Principle	Essence and principle of operation
Accounting for landscape boundaries	It provides for the assessment of background and derivative territories within landscape allocations, which allows establishing anthropogenic-differentiation series of the territory under different types of land use.
Optimal functioning and landscape-ecological balance	This implies the fact that the management and design of protected areas should be focused on their optimization. The created landscape maps allow us to establish the optimal ratio of productive, environmental and nature protection functions of the main components of the territorial community.
Comparative geographical and conjugate analysis	It includes a comparison of the landscape structure in one area over a certain period of time, which allows to establish a connection with the original invariant, the direction, reversibility, degree and scale of transformation of the territory, and the loss of landscape and resource diversity.
Allocation of ecotone territories	It is a prerequisite for landscape mapping, as landscape ecotones are the most vulnerable to anthropogenic impact, which must be taken into account when planning.
Accounting for the ecological framework and landscape diversity of the territory	It allows you to highlight the natural diversity of the territory and landscape infrastructure on the landscape map, which together forms the ecological framework and determines the sustainability and stability of natural and agricultural systems of the territorial community.
Preserving environmental well-being and attractiveness	This includes the designation of landscapes of aesthetic value and ensuring the creation of a healthy environment for the population of the territorial community.
Natural resource and economic feasibility	It focuses on identifying territories characterized by high natural resource potential that are recommended for agricultural land use at minimal cost.
The principle of accounting for the sustainability of the territory	It involves determining the possible reaction of the territory to reclamation or pasture impacts and the ability of natural complexes to return to their original structural and functional regime.

At the regional level, landscape transformation trends may differ depending on specific conditions. In regions with intensive mining, there are significant changes in relief and environmental pollution. In coastal areas, the risk of coastal erosion is increasing due to rising sea levels and extreme weather conditions

(Figure 1). Land use is a key factor determining the development of territorial communities. Changes in land use can have both positive and negative consequences for communities, affecting the economy, environment, and social sphere.

Fig. 1. Digital map of the agricultural landscape of the land territory with selected plots (example)

The economic development of territorial communities largely depends on the efficient use of land resources. Changes in land use can contribute to the creation of new jobs, infrastructure development, and improved welfare, and the development of territorial land or tourism can be an important source of income for local communities. However, improper

planning and use of land can lead to economic losses and social conflicts [2].

Studying the impact of land use changes on territorial communities is extremely important for ensuring sustainable development, which allows identifying potential threats and opportunities, developing effective management and planning

strategies that take into account environmental, economic and social aspects. In this way, it is possible to ensure harmonious development of territories, preservation of natural capital and improvement of the quality of life of the population.

The importance of these components in planning the land use system on the territory of territorial communities is growing significantly. Territorial communities need material and financial resources to perform the functions of local self-government, which must acquire autonomy and independence in the ownership, management and use of communal and other forms of land.

Particular attention should be paid to improving the legal component of the institutional environment for the formation of the land use system of territorial communities, which involves analyzing the main trends in planning the development of the land use system, in particular: property relations, functional orientation, social significance, and land capitalization.

Thus, in order to ensure sustainable development of land use practices at the level of territorial communities, four groups of factors should be taken into account: environmental, public economic and social. However, all of these groups of factors are interrelated in one way or another, and all together are a single principle of greening the lands of territorial communities. Therefore, it can be concluded that when studying this area, the main emphasis should be placed on the principles and directions of strategic sustainable development of territories. The proposed strategic measures for planning and managing land use at the level of territorial communities are the basis for the further development of Ukraine's regions.

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